

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part XIII. Synthesis of some new 3, 5-Diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamido- benzeneazo) pyrazoles as Potential Antimicrobial Agents

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In the search for new antimicrobial agents and to establish the structure activity relationship, some new 3, 5-diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles have been synthesised by condensing 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-(*p*-bromo/chlorophenyl)-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones with a number of carbonyl reagents under different reaction conditions. The homogeneity and purity of the resulting compounds was tested by TLC. and elemental analysis. All the synthesised compounds were then subjected to their antimicrobial tests *in vitro* and majority of these were found considerably active.

IN continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some pyrazole derivatives having methoxyl and methyl groups in the phenyl rings attached at positions 3 and 5, the present communication describes the synthesis of new pyrazoles by replacing the methyl group by halogen atoms with a view to study the effect of this replacement on the antimicrobial activity and then compare the results among themselves and with those obtained earlier¹⁻⁵.

These were prepared by condensing 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-(*p*-bromo/chlorophenyl)-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, *p*-methylphenylhydrazine and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine. Earlier workers⁶⁻⁸ suggested that this method would theoretically yield a mixture of two isomeric pyrazoles depending upon the mode of enolization of the β -diketone. But the products synthesised by us when subjected to TLC. gave only one spot, thereby showing the formation of only one isomer. This is further supported by the fact that all the pyrazoles were obtained in fairly good yields ranging between 60-75%. All these derivatives were then subjected to screening *in vitro* against two micro organisms using cup-plate agar diffusion method.

Experimental

The different 1, 3-diaryl 2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones required for this work were prepared by the method already reported⁹.

Synthesis of 3 (or 5)-(p-methoxyphenyl)-5 (or 3)-(p-halophenyl)-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles. These were obtained by condensing 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-(*p*-halophenyl)-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones with appropriate carbonyl reagents under the reaction conditions described in earlier communications¹⁻⁵. The orange or red coloured solid which separated out was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid or DMF-ethanol mixture.

The results of the pharmacological tests indicate that the pyrazole derivatives show varying degree of activity against *E. coli* and are inactive against *S. aureus*. When these results are compared with those reported earlier¹, it becomes evident that introduction of halogen atom causes a decrease in the activity. However, on comparison with the pyrazole derivatives containing only the halogen atoms⁵, one could arrive at the conclusion that the presence of a methoxyl group causes an increase in the activity which is in confirmation of our earlier observations¹⁻⁴.

TABLE 1—3(OR 5) - (p-METHOXYPHENYL)-5(OR 3) - (p-CHLOROPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R ₁	M.P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
<i>R=H</i>						
1.	H (A)	286	BOF	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
2.	COCH ₃ (B)	288	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
3.	Ph (C)	241	SOF	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
4.	p-Cl.Ph (D)	246-7	RN	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ SCl ₂	(-)	(++)
5.	p-CH ₃ .Ph (E)	223-4	SRN	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(++)
6.	p-OCH ₃ .Ph(F)	226	OF	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
7.	Pyrimidyl (G)	300	SR	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₇ SCl	(-)	(+++)
<i>R=Ph</i>						
8.	(A)	187	DO	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
9.	(B)	184	O	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
10.	(C)	165-6	SOR	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
11.	(D)	171-2	OR	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ SCl ₂	(-)	(+)
12.	(E)	189-90	SROF	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(++)
13.	(F)	199	R	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
14.	(G)	308	SOR	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₇ SCl	(-)	(+++)
15.	4,6-(CH ₃) ₂ pyrimidyl(H)	208	YO	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₇ SCl	-	-
<i>R=p-NO₂.Ph</i>						
16.	(A)	246-7	O	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	(-)	(++)
17.	(B)	250-1	SYOF	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₆ SCl	(-)	(++)
18.	(D)	224	RO	C ₃₄ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ SCl ₂	(-)	(++)
19.	(E)	216	O	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	(-)	(++)
20.	(F)	203	SRO	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₆ SCl	(-)	(+)
21.	(H)	230-1	OR	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	-	-
<i>R=p-CH₃.Ph</i>						
22.	(A)	150-1	O	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
23.	(B)	136	OF	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
24.	(D)	197	OR	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₅ SCl ₂	(-)	(+)
25.	(E)	195	O	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
26.	(F)	224	O	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)

TABLE 2—3(OR 5) - (p-METHOXYPHENYL)-5(OR 3) - (p-BROMOPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R ₁	M.P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
<i>R=H</i>						
1.	(A)	284	O	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
2.	(B)	283	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
3.	(C)	248	ON	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
4.	(D)	255	BRO	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ SBrCl	(-)	(+)
5.	(E)	232-3	BOF	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
6.	(F)	228-9	RO	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
7.	(G)	300	SR	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₇ SBr	(-)	(+)
<i>R=Ph</i>						
8.	(A)	189-90	O	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
9.	(B)	186-7	O	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
10.	(C)	178	O	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
11.	(D)	167-8	OR	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ SBrCl	(-)	(+)
12.	(E)	190-1	BOR	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
13.	(F)	194-1	BRO	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
<i>R=p-NO₂.Ph</i>						
14.	(A)	236	BrR	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₆ SBr	(-)	(+)
15.	(B)	236-7	OR	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₆ SBr	(-)	(+)
16.	(C)	148	RF	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₆ SBr	(-)	(+)
17.	(D)	219	SO	C ₃₄ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ SBrCl	(-)	(+)
18.	(E)	212	SO	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₆ SBr	(-)	(++)
19.	(F)	194	RBr	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₆ SBr	(-)	(+)
<i>R=p-CH₃.Ph</i>						
20.	(A)	133	R	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(++)
21.	(B)	170	OF	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(++)
22.	(C)	152	R	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(++)
23.	(D)	197	O	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₅ SBrCl	(+)	(-)
24.	(E)	196-7	O	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(-)
25.	(F)	179	SO	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	-	-

B = Bright ; Br = Brownish ; D = Dark ; F = Flakes ; N = Needles ; R = Red ; S = Shining ; Y = Yellowish
All the pyrazole derivatives gave satisfactory analysis for C and H.

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